

AGRICULTURAL SITUATION IN INDIA

AUGUST, 2015

GENERAL SURVEY OF AGRICULTURE

FARM SECTOR NEWS

ARTICLES

Institutional Credit for Agriculture in
India since Reforms

Economic Liberalisation and Agricultural
Productivity in North-East India

Decomposition Analysis and acreage
Response of Tur in Eastern Vidarbha
Region of Maharashtra

AGRO ECONOMIC RESEARCH

Biotechnology in Agriculture:
Potential, Performance and Concerns

Loan Repayment Problem
in India

COMMODITY REVIEWS

Foodgrains
Commercial Crops

TRENDS IN AGRICULTURE: Wages & Prices

Economic Liberalization and Agricultural Productivity in North-East India

SURENDRA SINGH¹ AND ZORAMKHUMA²

Abstract

The present paper attempts to examine the impact of economic liberalization on agricultural production systems prevalent in the North-East region. Calculating agricultural productivity in money terms for two points of time — 1998-99 (liberalization period) and 2008-09 (post-liberalization), it is found that the central parts of Meghalaya plateau, the hill districts of Manipur and the Eastern parts of Arunachal Himalaya have witnessed very high rate of agricultural productivity. It happened due to two main reasons: first, a fast transformation of the food-grain dominated cropping pattern into commercial cropping because farmers wish to grow high value crops to maximize their profit and, secondly, the growing market economy and expanding road network in rural areas which have been helping in regulating agricultural products within and outside North-East Region.

Introduction

Economic reforms in India were initiated in 1991 through the process of trade liberalization of agricultural commodities and removal of subsidies on fertilizer and irrigation which was implemented gradually. New economic policy and liberalization leads to reduction of tariff rate for agriculture products from 113 per cent in 1990-1991 to 26 per cent in 1997-1998. This means that farmers now have relatively closer access to import new technology and better capital equipment as well as the option of adoption of better farming techniques which should lead to technical progress and, consequently, the productivity enhancement. Ultimately, it leads to rethinking of production technique and efficient utilization of inputs and technology.

Indian farmers are responding well to opportunities in commercial agriculture and diversifying to meet the rising demand for food products. Such trends show that the crop productivity is diversifying toward non-food grains and high-value commodities such as fruits and vegetables (Singh and Pal 2010). Increase in agricultural output and productivity is important for two reasons. First, higher production and productivity are crucial elements of agriculture to meet the growing demand for food and non-food agricultural products in both domestic and foreign markets. Secondly, an increase in productivity drives up agricultural income and improves the competitiveness of this sector (Coelli and Rao 2003, Singh and Chhetri 2012). It is noticed that there has been constant change in land use with the increasing pressure of population and consequent demand for food, development activities and technological improvements.

The economy of North-Eastern region is mainly rural and agrarian as it accommodates more than 88 per cent population in its rural areas, of which 80.5 per cent is engaged in agriculture and allied sectors of economy as per Census 2001 records. In every year, more than 2.7 million hectare of land is used for practising shifting cultivation. The shifting cultivators grow food grains, vegetables and also cash crops. In fact, the growers aim at growing crops in their land as they need for their family consumption. Despite increasing food consumption in the region, the percentage share of Gross Domestic State Product (GDSP) from agriculture has been continuously declining from 44.21 in early 1980's to 34.59 in early 1990's. In the region, the percentage share of agriculture in GSDP varies from 13.6 in Mizoram to 28.80 per cent in Nagaland (Table - 1).

TABLE 1 : GROSS STATE DOMESTIC PRODUCT FROM AGRICULTURE FOR 2009-10 AT CONSTANT PRICES 1999-2000
(FIGURES IN LAKHS RUPEES)

State	GSDP from Agriculture	Total GSDP	Percentage Share of Agriculture to Total GDSP
Assam	12,47,811	56,70,231	22.01
Arunachal Pradesh*	65,387	302,827	21.59
Manipur*	94,082	4,89,866	19.21
Meghalaya*	1,12,783	6,45,901	17.46
Mizoram*	35,633	2,62,033	13.60
Nagaland***	1,39,661	4,84,992	28.80
Tripura**	1,70,569	8,34,958	20.43
Total	18,65,926	86,90,808	21.47

Source : Central Statistics Office, MOSPI, Govt. of India, New Delhi, *2008-09, **2007-08, ***2006-07.

¹Professor Retd ²Research Scholar Department of Geography, North-Eastern Hill University, Shillong—793022 (India).

So far as agriculture of the North-East Region of the country is concerned, more than two-third area of the region is hilly; the plain and flat lands are limited to permanent cultivation. Highland paddy is the predominant crop of these lands, mixed with maize, ginger, chilies, beans, tuber crops, tobacco, cotton etc., to meet annual needs of the households. The choice of crop is consumption-oriented, except in some hill areas exposed to modern farming methods where single crop is taken in a given piece of land. Rice, maize, and wheat are important cereals while tuber crops such as tapioca, yams and sweet potato, oilseeds and sesamum, jute, mesta, ramie, cotton and pulses are all important crops of the region. Due to unique diversity of agro-ecological conditions owing to topographical variations, altitudinal differences and variation of soil fertility, a large number of fruits and plantation crops like coconut, cashew nut, areca nut, black-pepper and so on are cultivated. Vast area on the hill slopes under shifting cultivation provides an unlimited scope for expansion of horticulture-based industries in a phased manner as an alternative to the shifting cultivation.

Parallel to the other parts of the country, the agricultural practices in North-East India are mainly foodgrain dominated. According to the report of Economic Survey of India (2002), the total food grain production has increased from 170 million tonnes in 1991-92 to 203 million tonnes in 2000-01 after the implementation of new economic policies. The rice production increased from 86.95 million tonnes in 1999-2000 to 93.78 million tonnes in 2004-2005. The spectacular improvement in rice production was due to adoption of HYVs of seeds, utilization of irrigation facilities, application of fertilizer, plant protection measures and use of improved farm implement has not been realized to a great extent in North-Eastern states (Viraktamath et al. 2008).

Issues Addressed

In the fast changing agricultural pattern from foodgrain to commercial crops, the rapid increase in the productivity and production levels within the ambit of fast rate of GDP in India during the half of 21st century, it is still not clear that the same rate of change of agricultural productivity was recorded in North Eastern Region which is called the replica of India in the context of its physical structure and socio-cultural diversity (include Study area map). The issues of productivity increase and changes in cropping pattern are relevant to probe into the productivity pattern of pre- and post-liberalization periods in North East where horticulture on the hill slope and permanent intensive cultivation in the valley flats have been practised for long.

Despite age-old traditional practices of agriculture (shifting cultivation), there seems to be significant changes in the use of agricultural implements from early traditional implements to modern small sized tractor, power tiller and so on. But indigenous system of irrigation is still continuing

because it is suitable for hill topography. Land reform system is complex and difficult task in North-East India because the land-system is governed by traditions and customs in most of the hill areas, but there has been written land-law in Assam (Land and Revenue Regulation-1886), in Tripura (The Tripura Land-Revenue and Land Reforms Act-1960) and in Manipur (Manipur Land-Revenue and Land Reforms Act-1960) (Goswami 2006). Jhum Land Regulation Act of 1970 was only the land legislation in Nagaland, while the land relations in Meghalaya are guided entirely by unwritten traditions and customary laws.

Under such situation of changing environment of agricultural practices, the issues of the changes in productivity over time may be the consequence of increasing population pressure, technological enhancement and implementation of economic liberalization policies of the government. There are numerous studies at global as well as Indian contexts which follow two schools of thought on development of agricultural production; first follows the Marxian economic view of population growth that compels to increase agricultural production (Boserup 1965). The second school follows western concept of technological enhancement and production increase (Binswanger 1978). However, the validity of such premises is to be tested to take into account North East India where a significant variation in agro-ecological conditions and socio-economic milieu is prevalent.

Keeping this view in mind, the main issues of productivity increase are to be addressed by considering productivity variations within the zone and changes over time in respect to changes in cropping pattern during implementation of new policies of economic liberalization (effect of road transport and increasing market facilities). Therefore, attention is focused towards the changing pattern of agricultural productivity and its area-specific factors.

Study Area

The North East region of India is formed by seven sister states- Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland and Tripura. The total geographical area of the region is about 8 percent of the total geographical area of the country accounting for about 263 lakh hectares.

Physiographically, the North East Region is divided into three main sub-divisions-(i) Hills and Mountains, (ii) Plateau and (iii) the basin of Brahmaputra and Barak River. The Hills and Mountains and basin alone account for approximately 65 percent of the total land area while Brahmaputra valley and Meghalaya plateau cover 22 percent and 13 per cent respectively. There is a wide altitudinal variation ranging from 300 m to 5000 m. The temperature varies from tropical plains of Barak Valley to temperate hills. The region is well known for very high rainfall combined with very high humidity. All these factors

affect regional agricultural systems in a vivid manner. About 70 percent of the area is under forest cover. The main strength of the region lies in its vast natural resources especially in its forest, water, flora and fauna diversity within which different types of agriculture has been practicing. Due to vast variations in agro-ecological conditions of surface features, the North-East Region has significant areas variations in crop-growth systems and productivity variation. It has been studied in understanding the productivity pattern.

Measurement of Agricultural Production and Productivity

The concept of agricultural productivity is related to production factors and the production of a particular factor. Since total production of agriculture is result of various factors like land (referring to physical conditions of land), labour (engaged human and cattle force to produce) and capital (the technology), the productivity has been defined relatively in terms of production per unit of land (land productivity), production produced per unit labour (labour productivity) and production per unit of capital (in the form of technology) invested in land operation.

In present case, agricultural productivity refers to land productivity that is defined as total agricultural output per unit of cultivated area. However, a total agricultural output was conceived by many geographers/economists differently by considering the crop areas coverage and crop-yield to convert yield into total production. Going through the literature available on measurement of agricultural output, it is widely accepted that agricultural production is the result of combinations of infra-structural elements, viz, physical, techno-economic, socio-cultural, etc. by which agricultural efficiency is influenced (Singh and Chauhan, 1977). Therefore, the study of agricultural production may be done by considering three different aspects such as output per unit area, output per man-hour and input-output ratio (Stamp, 1960). Much has been written by economists and agricultural scientists on how to measure productivity. Different concepts and corresponding measures of productivity may be appropriate for different purposes, though they all express some measures of output relative to agricultural production factors. Since market price of agricultural products influencing factor of agricultural output, the economists considered three elements of agriculture (Area, Yield and Price of crops) to measure the total output in terms of money value. For the purpose of aggregated agricultural output, the following standard formula used by Bhalla and Tyagi (1989) and Singh (1994), has been adopted:

$$O = \sum (A_i \cdot Y_i \cdot P_i) \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Then agricultural productivity is simply the output per unit of cultivated land as

$$Y = (O/A), \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

where, Y = agricultural productivity per area unit, A_i = area of ith Crop, Y_i = yield of ith Crop, P_i = harvest price of ith Crop, O = total agricultural output in its money term.

For the purpose of analyzing the changing pattern of agricultural productivity in North-East India, the conversion of area and yield of the various crops has been used for two points of time (i.e., 1998-99 and 2008-09). Thus, the agricultural output of each of the areas unit (District) has been calculated by converting crop production into its money term with the help of multiplying total production of each crop by its constant harvest price of the base year (1998-99).

Change in agricultural productivity over time is simply the difference in productivity levels between base year (t₀) and current year (t₁). Considering such differences at district level, the pattern of productivity changes are shown to understand and its processes.

The regional analysis of agricultural productivity is solely based on secondary data collected district wise from Ministry of Information and Technology, Government of India and other government publications through government websites, namely www.agricoop.nic.in and www.indianstat.com. As there is significant areal variation in harvest price of various crops, the district wise crop-price data were used. Farm harvest price of 1998-99 is considered for both the time periods, 1998-99 the liberalization phase and 2008-09 the Post-liberalization phase of economic growth. A total number of 32 crops were included for the calculation of the total agricultural output. In order to show the causes of productivity change, these crops were grouped into two sub-groups as foodgrains (rice, maize, wheat, arhar, bajra, jowar, masoor, moong, small millets, urad and gram) and commercial crops (jute, cotton, sugercane, arecanut, banana, nigerseed, tapioca, black-pepper, turmeric, chillies, ginger, mustard and rapeseeds, castor seeds, linseeds, sunflower, soya bean, potato, onion, bean, pea and sweet potato). The required farm harvest price data for each of the crops for the year 1998-99 were collected from the government websites mentioned above, published by Directorate of Economics and Statistics, Ministry of Agriculture, Government of India.

Agricultural Productivity Pattern during Liberalization and Post Liberalization Periods

Classifying districts into five productivity classes, namely: (i) very high productivity (above Rs. 20,000/ha), (ii) high (Rs. 15,000/ha - Rs. 20,000/ha), (iii) medium (Rs. 10,000/ha- Rs. 15,000/ha), (iv) low (Rs. 5,000/ha-Rs. 10,000/ha) and (v) very low productivity (below Rs. 5,000/ha), the general productivity pattern for the years 1998-99 and 2008-09 are curved out to analyze the processes of productivity change during the post-liberalization period.

Areas of High and Very High Productivity (Above Rs. 15,000/ha) were confined only in the Manipur hills and Imphal Valley including Southern Parts of Naga hills and Jaintia hills of Meghalaya plateau during liberalization period (Fig- 1A). Such areas were expanded remarkably from 24.43% of total cropped area (17 districts) to more than 50% (47 districts) during the period of post-liberalization (1998-99 to 2008-09). The surrounding areas of Patkai hills and Eastern part of Arunachal Himalaya and

entire Meghalaya plateau including Karbi hills of Assam were included in the expanded areas of high productivity during the post-liberalization period. An area of Central part of Brahmaputra plains is also increased productivity to be the part of high productivity category during the same period of time (Fig.-1B). In fact, the comparison of these patterns shows the absolute picture of productivity change. More detail patterning of change is shown by highlighting district wise decadal change in productivity levels.

Figure 1 Levels of Agricultural Productivity in (a) 1998-99 and (b) 2008-09

Variation and Decadal Change in Agricultural Productivity Levels (1998-99 to 2008-09)

The inter-district variations in agricultural productivity change are the visualization of regional inequalities in agricultural productivity levels. Such variation over time shows the speed of agricultural transformation. There are two dimensions considered for the measurement of change in productivity levels: the degree of productivity variability within the productivity classes and, secondly, the regional patterns of productivity change over time. The degree of variability is measured statistically by calculating Coefficient of Variation (CV) that is the ratio of Standard Deviation (SD) with the mean as $CV(\%) = (SD/Mean) * 100$. The regional pattern of productivity change was shown by mapping the inter district variation in productivity change.

The districts were classified into five classes as (i) the Areas of High Productivity Increase (Above Rs. 20,000/ha), (ii) Moderate Increase (Rs. 10,000/ha to 20,000/ha), (iii) Low Increase (Rs 0 to 10,000/ha), (iv) Moderate Decline (Rs. 0 to 3,000/ha) and (v) Fast Decline (More than Rs. -3,000/ha) and mapped the emerging pattern of change.

As far as variation in productivity level is concerned, the productivity level of each productivity class has been increased after the implementation of liberalization policy. However, there has been in increasing degree of productivity variation. For example, a noticeable increase in the degree of variation from 15.08 % to 58.73 % was noticed within the very high category of productivity level (Table-2).

TABLE 2 : VARIATION IN PRODUCTIVITY LEVELS IN VARIOUS PRODUCTIVITY CLASS IN THE NORTH EAST INDIA (1998-99 AND 2008-09)

Sl. No.	Productivity Class (Rs.ha)	No.of Districts		Mean Pro-ductivity level (Rs.ha)		Standard Deviation (Rs.ha)		Coefficient of variation (%)	
		1998-99	2008-09	1998-99	2008-09	1998-99	2008-09	1998-99	2008-09
1	Very High (Rs. 20,000 above)	7	24	24544	37882	3702	22246	15.08	58.73
2	High (Rs. 15,000- 20,000)	10	23	17945	17600	1333	1231	7.41	7.60
3	Medium (Rs. 10,000 -15,000)	10	18	12410	13431	1163	1421	9.38	10.58
4	Low (Rs. 5,000 -10,000)	24	5	7296	7204	1318	795	18.06	11.04
5	Very Low (below Rs 5000)	72	2	2722	4671	1781	163	65.45	3.50

It means that an obliterated pattern of productivity distribution emerges in the North East Region during the liberalization period. In fact, low productivity areas of central Manipur valley were expanded towards entire Meghalaya plateau and most of Arunachal Himalayas due to changes in cropping pattern. The Areas of high increase in Productivity (Above Rs.20,000/ha) are found in the ten districts of North East region which are generally located in the Arunachal North and Meghalaya Plateau. The highest degree of change is experienced in the districts of Dibang

Valley (Rs.93,535/ha) followed by East Garo Hills (Rs. 62,085/ha), Ri-Bhoi (Rs. 61,503/ha), N.C. Hills (Rs. 55,396/ha), East Siang (Rs. 43,088), East Khasi Hills (Rs. 38,367/ha), Lohit (Rs. 25,507/ha), Changlang (Rs. 20,972/ha), West Khasi (Rs. 20,972/ha) and West Garo Hills (Rs. 20,191/ha). The areas of rapid change of agricultural productivity are situated in the hill area of Meghalaya that has potential for the cultivation of horticulture crops. Another area is in the loop of Eastern Himalaya located in the Eastern mountain parts of Arunachal Pradesh (Fig.-2).

Figure 2 : Changes in Agricultural Productivity (1998-99 to 2008-09)

Process of Productivity Change

No doubt, the expansion of the areas of high productivity change in the North-East region is the result of two major forces accelerated during the liberalization phase of economic development. First is closely related to the mobilization of tribal rural-based economies through the new intensive and options of agricultural production increase given by the State Government. For example, implementation of watershed management and rural-livelihood programmes for the hill states of the North-East provided a sound base for alterations of their traditional means of cultivation in these areas of high productivity increase. The conversion of traditional system of rice - based Jhum into broom- based cultivation especially in the central part of Meghalaya, the replacement of traditional horticultural crops by new HYVs of crops to yield more production in Nagaland and Arunachal states and the introduction of more remunerative crops like Tea, Cashew nuts and Orange crops in Garo Hills and in many parts of Meghalaya plateau are main causes of productivity increase.

The second main cause of productivity increase in the hills and a marginal area of Brahmaputra plains are the fast growth of town-economies and intensification of road network that regulated the agricultural production within and outside the region. For example, increasing role of State capitals like Aizawl as collection center of agricultural production changed the cropping pattern from food grains

to commercial crops. Increasing market facilities to sale the agricultural products in hill towns and larger urban centers of the plains have changed the cropping pattern fast from low value crops to high value horticultural crops in the cropping pattern of these high productivity areas. In fact, Hills and mountains have better agro-ecological conditions to grow horticulture crops and vegetables in the North-Eastern Region. Increasing area under commercial crops increases agricultural output during liberalization period. That is why, the marginal contribution of the output of commercial crops to the total agricultural output during liberalization period raised significantly the productivity to about 40.1% from 37.69% to 78.00% in the areas of very high productivity classes (Table-3and4). Further, such changing situations of agricultural practices during the liberalization phase of development diversify the productivity pattern as degree of areal variability increases significantly. From geographical point of view, areal variation in productivity mainly depends on the physical factors like topography, temperature, rainfall, soil type, the socio-economic factors related to population density (creates demand for food).Such facts have also been highlighted in the other studies conducted on agricultural productivity in the North-East India. The change in crop productivity through increasing area and output of commercial crops is also visualized in the upper part of Brahmaputra valley as vegetables and spices gained place in cropping pattern (Singh and Talukdar2012).

TABLE 3 : TOTAL AREA AND OUTPUT IN DIFFERENT PRODUCTIVITY CLASSES IN NORTH-EAST INDIA IN 1998-99

Productivity Class	No. of District	Total Area (ha) and Output (Rs. Lakh)							
		Food Grains				Commercial Crops			
		Area to Total		Output to Total		Area to Total		Output to Total	
		Area (ha)	%	(Rs. Lakh)	%	Area (ha)	%	(Rs. Lakh)	%
Very High (Above Rs. 20000)	7	86,273	94.75	11,772.67	62.31	4,785	5.25	7,119.54	37.69
High (Rs.15000-20000)	10	1,52,587	88.68	22,871.03	74.94	19,483	11.32	7,648.96	25.06
Medium (Rs. 10000-15000)	10	2,60,248	93.67	28,864.02	81.24	17,597	6.33	6,664.06	18.76
Low (Rs. 5000-10000)	24	3,63,857	85.55	31,319.81	89.33	61,437	14.45	3,741.08	10.67
Very Low (Below Rs. 5000)	21	72,070	63.98	3,693.60	85.78	40,569	36.01	614.34	14.26
Total/average	72	9,19,997	85.33	98,521.12	78.72	1,42,922	21.86	25,787.98	21.29

Source : Compiled by the Authors

TABLE 4 : TOTAL AREA AND OUTPUT IN DIFFERENT PRODUCTIVITY CLASSES IN NORTH-EAST INDIA IN 2008-09

Productivity Class	No. of District	Total Area (ha) and Output (Rs. Lakh)							
		Food Grains				Commercial Crops			
		Area to Total		Output to Total		Area to Total		Output to Total	
		Area (ha)	%	(Rs. Lakh)	%	Area (ha)	%	(Rs. Lakh)	%
Very High (Above Rs. 20000)	24	6,96,568	73.32	69,287	22.00	2,53,414	26.68	2,45,524	78.00
High (Rs.15000-20000)	23	15,14,191	82.22	1,70,536	53.04	3,27,389	17.78	1,50,968	46.96
Medium (Rs.10000-15000)	18	12,86,263	83.00	1,12,399	54.19	2,63,353	17.00	95,003	45.81
Low (Rs.5000-10000)	5	51,155	93.11	2,864	73.12	3,784	6.89	1,053	26.88
Very Low (Below Rs. 5000)	2	7,558	87.94	258	63.78	1,036	12.05	1,46	36.21
Total/avg.	72	35,55,735	83.91	3,55,344	53.22	8,48,976	16.08	49,2694	46.77

Source : Compiled by Authors

A recent study on changing agricultural pattern conducted in the central Brahmaputra plains choosing Nagaon district of agricultural dominance which is located between North Cachar- Karbiang long hills of Meghalaya plateau and flood plains of Brahmaputra river having three distinct micro- topographic features: the narrow river valleys of foot-hill topography, the built- up plains of old-alluvial formed by Kapili and Jamuna rivers, and the seasonal flood plains of charlands (river beds), beels (islands), oxbow-dry lakes and lowland green grazing grounds where the Muslim peasants of immigrant origins are settled, concludes that, despite much higher density of population (711 persons/sq km) and strong agriculture base of rural economy (as it accounts for about 70% to total population of the district) and rural consumption pattern (that is based on their own grown food), there has been remarkable increase in the areas of horticulture (fruits, vegetables and nuts) and cash crops (fibers, spices, sugarcane and tea). Horticulture accounted for 5.00 % and cash crops 12.26% in the district in 1990-91 while 70.00 % cultivated land was under rice cultivation. The area was increased under horticultural crops from 5.00 % to 9.99% and under cash crops from 5.00% to 17.25 % during the last 15 years (1990-91 to 2005-06), while the area under rice cultivation remained almost same (Saikia 2012: 83-138).

In spite of occasional floods in the flood plains situated in the central parts of Brahmaputra Valley, the Nagaon area of strong rural economy, the intensity of cropping was

higher in these areas than the other parts of the district as across the district intensity remained low (113.78 to 115.00%) during the period of liberalization. Literacy and irrigation do not have impact on cropping intensity. However, rural population has positive correlation with intensity ($r= 0.90$) (Saikia 2012:159-169). It means that food grain consumption is the main factor of productivity increase than technology. Despite fast changes in productivity pattern, market access and market economies are not yet influencing the cropping pattern in this area of growing agricultural economy.

The agricultural productivity is sensitive to the high value crops like vegetables and cash crops which raised productivity especially in the *chars* of low lying areas where wet alluvial fertile soils, gradually increased use of chemical fertilizers and laborious. Muslim peasants who grow three crops in a year in these areas are main causes of increasing productivity and commercialization in agriculture. However, these changes are much slower in Brahmaputra valley than the hills and mountains areas. In the hill areas, horticulture, floriculture and high value crops like broom-grass in Jhum areas of Meghalaya plateau are important crops. On the whole, it is obvious that increasing output of commercial crops increases the productivity. The areas of low increase in the output of commercial crops have very slow increase (output Rs. 15,000/ha) in productivity. On the other hand, the areas of high decadal increase in the output of commercial crops (60-80%) have faster changes in agricultural productivity (Fig. -3).

Figure 3 : Increase in Agricultural Productivity as Output of Commercial Crop increases

Concluding Remarks

There has been fast change in agricultural productivity during the liberalization phase of economic development in the North-East Region. Only a few patches of high productivity (in the hill areas) have been expanded up to the half of the North-East area during the last ten years. It happened due to the changing food grain dominated crop pattern (1998-99) to horticulture and fruits dominated crop (2008-09). Hill areas have potential to expand horticultural crops because of humid climate, fertile soils and bio-diversity in this area. Such interesting changes of agricultural productivity are characterized as:

- (a) The areas having moderate productivity level in 1998-99 have experienced fast change in productivity during the decade considered for. In 2008-09, about 65 percent areas (47 out of 72 districts) fall under the categories having very high productivity levels. This means that agricultural productivity is increased in the moderate productivity areas in the region. These fast changing areas have experienced fast development in rural road connectivity that has altered cropping pattern from food grains to commercial crops. The main driving factors of productivity increase in the North-East Region are the improvement of agricultural infrastructure (irrigation, HYV seeds and road density) that has created situation for commercialization in agriculture.
- (b) The Central Meghalaya Plateau and North-Eastern part of Arunachal Pradesh Himalaya have the highest increase in agricultural productivity. The role of Horticulture Directorates of various states is recognizable. These Departments of state Governments have been helping for long to increase areas under cash crop cultivation. During the last ten years of liberalization phase, commercial crops became popular in the hill areas. That is why the agricultural productivity rose rapidly. Farmers introduced new commercial crops by replacing their traditional crops. Improvement of roads network in this area also leads to the farmer behavior for selling their agricultural product in the market. However, productivity pattern become more diversified.
- (c) Some areas of low level of productivity located in the middle and lower parts of Brahmaputra Valley also emerged as the areas of the moderate productivity increase due to increasing areas under high value commercial crops. In the surroundings of the urban centers, productivity boosted fast because of diffusion effect of growing market-economy. For example, Kamrup district of Assam accounted as low productivity area Rs. 3,851/ha in pre-liberalization period (1998-99). It was raised to Rs.17,359/ha during the liberalization period due to direct impact of urbanization.

REFERENCE

- Bhalla, G. S. and D. S. Tyagi (1989): *Pattern in Indian Agricultural Development- A District Level Study*, Institute for Studies in Industrial Development, New Delhi
- Binswanger, H. P (1978): *Introduced Technological Change-Evaluation of Thought*, Johns Hopkins University Press
- Boserup, E. (1965): *The Conditions of Agricultural Growth*, George Allen and Unwin, London
- Coelli, T. J. and D. S. P. Rao (2003): *Total Factor Productivity Growth in Agriculture: A Malmquist Index Analysis of 93 Countries, 1980-2000*, Paper presented at the International Association of Agricultural Economics Conference, Durban, August
- Goswami, P. J. (2006): *Changing Agricultural Scenario in North-East India in the Era of Globalization*, Paper Present at Changing Agricultural Scenario in North-East India (2004: Shillong).
- Saikia, D. (2012): *Agricultural Development in Nagaon District, Assam: A Geographical Analysis*, Ph. D. Thesis Submitted to Department of Geography, Gauhati University, Guwahati.
- Singh, S. and Chhetri P. (2013): Regional Processes and Pattern of Agricultural growth in India after Economic Liberalization, *Agricultural Situation in India*, Vol. LXX (3): June 2013
- Singh, A. and S. Pal (2010): The Changing Pattern and Sources of Agricultural Growth in India, *The Shifting Patterns of Agricultural Productivity in World Wide*, The Midwest Agri-business Trade Research and Information Center, Iowa State University, USA.
- Singh, S. (1994): *Agricultural Development in India: A Regional Analysis*, Kaushal Publications, Shillong.
- Singh, S. and M. Talukdar (2012): Economic Liberalization and Agricultural Productivity—A Case Study of Sadiya Sub-Division of Upper Brahmaputra Valley, *Agricultural Situation in India*, Vol. LXIX (6): 301-309
- Singh, S. and V. S. Chauhan (1977): Measurement of Agricultural Productivity—A Case Study of Uttar Pradesh, *Indian Geographical Review of India*, 39: 222-31
- Stamp, L.D. (1960): *Our Developing World*, Faber and Faber, London
- Viraktamath, B. C., N. S. Rani and V. P. Bhadana (2008): *Rice Production Constrain and Strategies for Sustainable Development*, Sustainable Hill Agriculture, Today and Tomorrow Publication, New Delhi.